

Updates on Lassa Fever in Nigeria

Clement Ugochukwu Nyenke ¹, Felix Eedee Konne ², and Roseanne Adah Ikpeama¹

¹Department of Medical Laboratory Science, PAMO University of Medical Sciences, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

²Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Abstract

Nigeria, with population of approximately 200,000,000 people and a 2.6% annual growth rate has had several disease outbreaks in the last ten years, including Lassa fever. Lassa virus (LASV) is a biosafety level-4 virus that causes Lassa fever (LF). Ingestion of consumables tainted with urine or faeces, as well as inhalation of droplets by its natural host, the Multimammate rat, are frequent ways in which it is spread to people (*Mastomys natalensis*). This is accomplished by infecting endothelial cells with alpha-dystroglycan cell-surface receptors (alpha-DG). The majority of human cases of Lassa fever normally occur between December and April during the dry season. According to the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control, there were 7,077 suspected cases overall as of week 42 (17th - 23rd October, 2022), with the age group most frequently affected being 21 to 30 years (NCDC). In week 41(2022), there were seven new confirmed cases, an increase from the previous week's four. These cases were recorded in the states of Ondo, Edo, Ebonyi, and Cross River. The South-Southern geopolitical zone's Edo State and the Southwest geopolitical zone's Ondo State have seen the most of the virus' spread since December 2016. The Nigerian government has implemented a number of strategies, including the activation of the National Emergency Operations Centre alert mode, the creation of state public health operation centres, the dispatch of National Rapid Response Teams (NRRT), case management, and IPC training for medical professionals. Additionally, the Nigerian government has declared intentions to develop new medications and vaccines with facilities at the Federal Medical Center in Owo, the Alex Ekwueme Federal University Teaching Hospital, and the Irrua Specialist Teaching Hospital in Edo state. and Bauchi State Teaching Hospital. With the use of Lassa virus vaccines raising important questions about cost, stability and accessibility, rodent control and further researches as well as public health campaigns remains effective ways to prevent Lassa fever in endemic countries. Keywords: fever, infection, lassa, virus

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Corresponding author:
Clement Ugochukwu Nyenke
clemnyenke@yahoo.com

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1 Introduction

With the COVID-19 epidemic still fresh in people's minds, infectious diseases are a source of worry for both governmental and non-governmental groups worldwide. Infectious microorganisms are the cause of some diseases that have a high prevalence of morbidity and mortality. The Lassa virus (LASV), a biosafety level-4 virus that causes Lassa fever (LF), was initially discovered in 1969 in Lassa, Borno state, Nigeria (Frame *et al.* 1970). LF continues to be a significant clinical, financial, and health security burden for affected communities and nations. LASV is unquestionably a West African phenomenon, according to epidemiological study and surveillance. It is common in Nigeria and a few other West African countries, including Sierra Leone, Liberia, and Guinea (Bowen *et al.* 2000), and infrequent imported cases have been noted in Europe and North America (Kofman, Choi, and Rollin 2019). In West Africa, there have been between 100,000 and 300,000 new cases of Lassa fever reported, with a monthly fatality rate of 5,000 (Izah, Ovuru, and Ogbu 2022). Nigeria, however, bears the heaviest load in Sub-Saharan Africa (Okwor *et al.* 2018; NCDC 2021). In Nigeria, the federal capital as well as many states and each of the country's six geopolitical zones have recorded

cases of Lassa fever. However, since December 2016, the main epicentres of the infection in Nigeria have been Ondo State in the Southwest geopolitical zone and Edo State in the South-Southern geopolitical zone. LF, a single-stranded RNA virus, circulates throughout the entire body (Healing and Gopal 2001; Johnson *et al.* 1987). The main contributor to viraemia is a delayed or defective cellular immune response (Chen and Cosgriff 2000). Antibodies to the virus have been detected in 21% of Nigerians, 4-5% of Guineans, and 8-52% of Sierra Leoneans, according to publications (McCormick *et al.* 1987; Lukashovich, Clegg, and Sidibe 1993). On the basis of instances recorded in staff members of the International Committee of the Red Cross, the United States Mission in Sierra Leone, the Central African Republic, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Mali, and Senegal, it has been determined that all of these nations are seropositive. Travelers to Germany, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom have reported a few isolated incidents (McCormick *et al.* 1987; Lukashovich, Clegg, and Sidibe 1993; Tomori *et al.* 1988).

1.1 Route of Transmission

Multimammate rats (*Mastomys natalensis*), which are widespread in west, central, and east Africa (Healing and Gopal 2001) and frequently breed, are the virus's natural hosts. They are without a doubt the most prevalent rodent in tropical Africa, and they are mostly found in rural areas where there are more houses than nearby open spaces (McCormick *et al.* 1987). Humans most frequently contract the Lassa virus through ingesting or inhalation (CDC 2014). *Mastomys* rats can contract the virus directly by touching contaminated objects, consuming tainted food, or contacting open wounds or cuts. The virus is spread by the rodents' urine and faeces. Contact with another person can spread it. Direct contact transmission occurs frequently because *Mastomys* rodents frequent areas where homes are located and frequently consume leftovers and badly maintained food. *Mastomys* rodents are occasionally used as food. Inhaling tiny airborne particles contaminated with the excreta of infected rodents can potentially result in contact with the virus. Cleaning tasks like sweeping may result in this aerosol or airborne transmission (CDC 2014). In addition to coming into contact with infected rodents directly (CDC 2014), individuals can also contract the Lassa virus through coming into contact with their blood, tissue, secretions, or excretions. Skin-to-skin contact or other casual contact that doesn't include the exchange of bodily fluids cannot transmit the Lassa virus. In clinical settings when proper personal protective equipment (PPE) is either unavailable or not used, nosocomial transmission, also known as person-to-person transfer, is common. The Lassa virus may also be disseminated by tainted medical items like discarded needles (CDC 2014). Rats identified in houses where individuals have the virus are 10 times more likely to be seropositive for it than rats found in households where the virus is not present (Keenlyside *et al.* 1983). People who ingest rats are twice as likely as those who do not to have viral antibodies, and deafness, a complication of Lassa fever, is four times as prevalent (Meulen *et al.* 1996). Approximately 80% of the population is infected, but only 20% develop severe multisystem disease. Six to twenty-one days are required for incubation (WHO 2000).

1.2 Pathogenesis

After transmission, the Lassa virus mostly attacks endothelial cells. The cell-surface receptor alpha-dystroglycan (alpha-DG), (Bowen *et al.* 2000) a flexible receptor for proteins of the extracellular matrix, is the method through which the Lassa virus enters the host cell. The alpha-dystroglycan receptor, a widely expressed cell surface receptor that is unrelated to clathrin, caveolin, dynamin, or actin, is the mechanism through which the Lassa virus enters cells through endocytosis. Contrary to most encapsulated viruses, which enter cells through clathrin-coated pits and connect to their receptors in a pH-dependent manner, this type of virus does not encapsulate its genetic material. After entering the cell, vesicular trafficking quickly transports the viruses to endosomes. The

envelope glycoproteins of the (Bowen *et al.* 2000) Lassa virus enable a pH-dependent binding and membrane fusion, protecting the virus against endosomal degradation. The clinical illness's initial signs and symptoms include a fever, generalised weakness, and a malaise that resembles the flu. Cough, sore throat, and a horrible headache could also be present. Additionally typical are gastrointestinal symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, and diarrhoea. Lassa fever may be difficult to distinguish from other acute, unexplained febrile infections that are widespread in West Africa based solely on the symptoms that are currently present (McCormick *et al.* 1987; Walker *et al.* 1982). Although Lassa fever does not typically present with hemorrhagic signs, vascular dysfunction is likely a significant contributor to the pathobiology of the illness given its association with a poor prognosis for survival. Increased vascular permeability is indicated by pericardial effusions, pleural effusions, and facial edema. Eight to ten days after the disease's first onset, Lassa fever patients frequently start recovering. A patient's condition might rapidly worsen between the sixth and tenth day of a severe illness, exhibiting signs such as severe pulmonary emphysema, acute respiratory distress, clinical encephalopathy, and possibly even coma and convulsions in addition to fatal shock. Although mucosal surface bleeding is frequently seen, it usually isn't sufficient to cause shock on its own (Walker *et al.* 1982). Sensorineural deafness is typically seen in patients with severe diseases or in the early phases of recovery in survivors (Cummins and editor 1990).

2 Nigeria and Updates on the Virus

2.1 Geographical characteristics of Nigeria

Nigeria shares boundaries with Chad to the north-east, Cameroon to the east, the Republic of Benin to the west, the Niger Republic to the north-west and north, and the Republic of Benin to the east, in addition to the Gulf of Guinea (the Atlantic Ocean), which serves as its southern border (Osawaru, Ogwu, and Ahana 2013). It is roughly 923,768 square kilometres in size. There are 36 states in Nigeria, including Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory. Like the rest of West Africa, she has two distinct seasons: the rainy or wet season and the dry season (WBG 2021). There are three different climate zones in the country, though: a tropical climate in the south, a tropical savannah climate in the centre, and a Sahel climate in the northern region. The savannah region has a distinct wet and dry season from April to October and November to March, respectively, with an average annual rainfall of about 1,200 mm. The southern area has the longest wet season in the nation, which normally lasts from March to October. It also receives the most yearly rainfall, with coastal plains receiving up to 4,000 mm (WBG 2021). With a population of around 200,000,000 and an annual population growth rate of 2.6%, Nigeria is the most populous nation in Africa. Nigeria has had a variety of disease outbreaks during the past ten years, including those brought on by COVID-19, monkeypox, yellow fever, cerebrospinal meningitis, Lassa fever, and Ebola (WBG 2021).

2.2 Updates: Incidence, Prevalence and Distribution

The Nigeria Centre for Disease Control regularly monitors the incidence, prevalence, and surveillance of Lassa fever in the country (NCDC). Weekly data collection is done for this. As of week 42 (17th–23rd October 2022), the FDA reported 7,077 suspected cases, with the age group most affected being 21–30 years. The male to female ratio has been shown to be 1:1.8 in confirmed cases (NCDC 2022a, 2022b). There were four more newly confirmed cases in week 41, bringing the total to seven (2022). These were reported by the states of Ondo, Edo, Ebonyi, and Cross River. At least one verified incidence has so far been recorded from 26 states and 105 Local Government Areas for the entire year of 2022. Ondo accounts for 33% of all validated cases, Edo for 25%, and Bauchi for 13%. Compared to the reported figures for the same time period in 2021, there are more suspected cases. As of the 42nd reporting week, no further healthcare workers have been reported to be afflicted (NCDC 2022b). Since December 2016, Lassa fever cases have been reported

in Bauchi, Taraba, Nasarawa, Plateau, Kogi, Benue, Kaduna, Ondo, Ebonyi, Delta, Edo, and Enugu. During that time, no instances of Lassa fever were noted in Bayelsa, Jigawa, Yobe, or Akwa-Ibom. So far in 2022, 2021, 2020, 2019, 2018, and December 2016–2017, reports of it have come from 23, 17, 27, 23, 23, and 19 states, including Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory (Izah, Ovuru, and Ogwu [2022](#)). Three states (Edo 42%, Ondo 34%, and Bauchi 8%) accounted for 84% of the total incidence of Lassa fever in 2021, while the other 14 states accounted for 16% of the incidence. This shows that the major epicentres of the 2021 virus are the states of Edo and Ondo. Incidence of Lassa fever in all 25 states was 25%, with the remaining three states (Edo 32%, Ondo 36%, and Ebonyi 7%) accounting for 75% (Izah, Ovuru, and Ogwu [2022](#)). This predicts that the states of Edo and Ondo would host the greatest virus epicentre in 2020. Data from 6 states in 2019 (Izah, Ovuru, and Ogwu [2022](#)) indicated that the main epicentre of the infection was located in the states of Edo, Plateau, and Ondo. (Plateau 34%, Taraba 5%, Bauchi and Ebonyi 7%, Edo 37%, Ondo 34%, and Plateau 34%) Six percent of cases of Lassa fever occur in the remaining 17 states. In 2018, Edo and Ondo states had the highest rates of Lassa fever, accounting for 44%, 25%, and 11% of all cases in those three states, respectively (NCDC [2018](#)). 20% of the cases came from the other 20 states (NCDC [2022b](#)). The South-Southern geopolitical zone's Edo State and the Southwest geopolitical zone's Ondo State have seen the majority of the virus's spread in Nigeria since December 2016 (Izah, Ovuru, and Ogwu [2022](#)). Ebonyi, Edo, and Ondo states had the highest incidence of infection with occurrences reported during outbreaks, accounting for 74.6% of confirmed cases between 2017 and 2018, according to additional research by (Amoo *et al.* [2021](#); Adebimpe *et al.* [2020](#); Usuwa *et al.* [2020](#)).

2.3 Public Health response

The Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) turned on the alert mode of the National Emergency Operations Centre in order to efficiently coordinate the response to Lassa fever across all sectors and disciplines. State public health operation centres have also been formed in the impacted states. The states of Bauchi, Benue, Ebonyi, Edo, Nasarawa, Ondo, Oyo, and Taraba have received national rapid reaction teams (NRRT) (WHO [2022](#)). Guidelines for case management and infection prevention and control (IPC) have been made accessible as a result of information obtained from healthcare professionals and the general public. Healthcare workers in treatment facilities have also received training in case management and IPC (WHO [2022](#)). Additionally, there is a recent increase in case discovery across all states as a result of improved surveillance for Lassa fever. The NCDC updates the situation and provides direction for potential future reaction plans using the supplied data (WHO [2022](#)). Medical response supplies have been sent to states and treatment centres, and confirmed cases are currently being treated at designated treatment facilities across the states. To ensure prompt sample processing, the seven national Lassa fever laboratories that the NCDC has authorised and that are capable of performing molecular testing are working at full capacity. To boost risk communication and community engagement, various tactics are being explored, including radio, print, social media, and television. The Federal Ministry of Environment is launching a Lassa fever environmental response campaign in affected states (WHO [2022](#)). The sustainable development goals must be accomplished in a healthy environment, which is connected to sustainable governance models that will involve numerous intersectoral links (Racioppi *et al.* [2020](#)). The importance of prevention measures, rapid diagnosis and treatment, assuring the availability of personal protective equipment, contact tracing, community awareness, and cross-border monitoring and surveillance are all points that (Grace, Egoh, and Udensi [2021](#)) underline further.

2.4 Risk assessment

Most cases of Lassa fever in people happen during the dry season, which lasts from December to April. The rainy season comes after the *Mastomys* rat breeding cycle (May – November). Since 90–95% of human infections are caused by either direct contact with infected *Mastomys* rats or indirect exposure (through contaminated food or household items contaminated by infected rats' waste), the high density and high circulation of Lassa fever virus in the rat population makes it possible that more people will get sick during the dry season. (WHO 2022) Reports say that over 80% of Lassa virus infections in humans don't cause any symptoms or are mild. The other 20%, on the other hand, show up with a fever and problems with several organs, with or without bleeding. The death rate for all infected people is thought to be around 1%, but it is much higher (around 15%) for people who are hospitalised with severe disease. (WHO 2022). A quick diagnosis speeds up the process of isolating a patient and getting them treatment. It also makes it less likely that a disease will spread from one person to another in a hospital. Early support care, treatment for symptoms, and rehydration help patients live longer. At the moment, the national level danger in Nigeria is thought to be high. Even though Nigeria has gotten better at preventing and controlling Lassa fever outbreaks, the risk level is still high because of a number of factors, such as better monitoring, diagnostic, and treatment capabilities. These include a rise in confirmed cases compared to previous epidemic seasons, gaps in surveillance and different levels of subnational response capacity, delays in sending samples to labs for testing, (WHO 2022). a drop in case management capacity because Lassa fever facilities were turned into COVID-19 health care facilities, and ineffective IPC procedures. The way these things work together shows how important it is to improve and strengthen the country's ability to find and stop Lassa fever epidemics.

2.5 Vaccine and Therapeutics production

The Nigerian government announced plans to make new treatments and a vaccine for Lassa fever in July 2022. This is to make sure that the number of Lassa fever cases goes down until it is no longer a threat to public health in Nigeria. The government said that the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI) are helping to make new treatments and vaccines (Adebowale-Tambe 2022). The Irrua Specialist Teaching Hospital in the state of Edo was chosen as the best place to make the film. The World Health Organization, the Alex Ekwueme Federal University teaching hospital, the Federal Medical Center in Owo, and the Bauchi State teaching hospital are also partners (Adebowale-Tambe 2022). According to (Adebowale-Tambe 2022), it has been said that a single-dose vaccine that would protect against both yellow fever and Lassa fever would be effective. Even though other substances have worked in test tubes, only ribavirin, which is an analogue of guanosine, has been used in therapy. People say that the medicine is the best way to treat lassa fever and that it does work (Fisher-Hoch and McCormick 2001; Buchmeier, Bowen, and Clarence 2001). Ribavirin doesn't work, though, if it's given late in the disease's course, after the viremia has reached its peak and physiological dysregulation has reached severe and often irreversible stages (Garry 2022; McCormick *et al.* 1986).

2.6 The road ahead-Prevention and Control

Lassa fever outbreaks can be stopped in Nigeria and the rest of West Africa by making rodent control a top priority (Garry 2022). More research needs to be done to find the best ways to use rodenticides that kill *Mastomys* and the intermediate hosts of LASV. In the same way, plans to stop *Mastomys* from breaking into homes should be looked at and made better. *Mastomys* may not come to your house in search of food or water if it has a well-sealed metal roof and strong walls. More research should be done on how *Mastomys* fits into the ecosystem and how it interacts with other rodent species, like *Rattus*. This species has a lot of genetic diversity, which needs to be taken into account.

Their use in Africa raises important questions about how much they cost, how stable they are, and how easy they are to get. Seroprevalence and incidence studies are now being done in West Africa using recombinant antigen ELISAs and PCR with reverse transcription of LASV. Based on these investigations, clinical trials will need to be done to see how well a vaccine or treatment works for people with Lassa fever (Gouglas *et al.* 2019). Seroprevalence and incidence research would also help with how to treat Lassa fever in countries where it is common. Even though research into possible preventive measures shouldn't be slowed down or stopped, the development of LASV vaccines and medicines has taken a good turn. Different situations or groups of people may need more than one vaccine. Travelers will care more about how well the protection works in the short term, while people who live in the Lassa fever zone will care more about how long the protection lasts. If a vaccine is shown to be safe and effective, public health workers in countries where the disease is common must work with the World Health Organization to come up with fair ways to give it out (WHO). (Gouglas *et al.* 2019) Along with making vaccines, there should also be effective treatments for Lassa fever. Combining medicines that work in different ways may be more effective than using any one medicine on its own. Also, there's no guarantee that a drug will be approved, so other options should be tried out just in case the ones that are there now don't work. Because there aren't enough non-human primate resources, pathogenesis research and critical evaluations of interventions will be harder to do in the future. This will make this part of the problem. Lassa fever should be treated in a way that takes key environmental factors into account. As with all evolutionary processes, it is likely that some people in areas where the disease is common will develop an immune response that will eventually lead to resistance. According to (Tewogbola and Aung 2020), the Yoruba people in Nigeria have become more resistant to LASV than people in other areas where it is common. The proposed emergency threshold and standard guidelines for managing Lassa fever by (Dan-Nwafor *et al.* 2019) will make it easier to track diseases.

3 Conclusion

Even though we have learned a lot, there are still big gaps in what we know about Lassa fever's immunology, epidemiology, ecology, and pathophysiology. More LASV outbreaks, the possibility that *Mastomys natalensis* and other rodent reservoirs will spread to new areas, how easy it is to get LASV and use it as a weapon, how often LASV is brought into North America and Europe, and the appearance of new LASV strains in populated West Africa have all pushed scientists to work harder on LASV countermeasures. According to (Garry 2022), there are no licenced vaccines or treatments for people right now, even though possible solutions are being thought about. Research on Lassa fever and other diseases that haven't been looked into enough will benefit from making it easier for national and African institutions to do clinical trials. The work of the African Centre of Excellence for the Genetics of Infectious Diseases (ACEGID), which is based at Redeemers University in Nigeria and is in charge of viral sequencing in the country, must be built on. Scientists from other African countries and other parts of the world are also trained by the AGEID in new technologies that are easy to use, such as nanopore sequencing. Now, there are many ways to describe the genetic diversity of LASV. All countries with this problem should take steps to make sure this capacity is available. In all areas where Lassa fever is common, the government must take steps to help weak health systems (Garry 2022; Koch *et al.* 2021). This will lessen the effects of the disease. It is important to keep spending money on expanding access to LASV diagnostics and non-drug treatments. Point-of-care diagnostics are very helpful in remote areas and hospitals where critically ill patients, including pregnant women, have a high risk of getting Lassa fever.

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